

Supplementary Files: Arguing for climate change adaptation finance – A bibliometric study

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Supplementary File S1: Overview of literature reviews in the field

Table S1: Overview of recent literature reviews in the field - by date and research area (urban adaptation or climate finance)

Note to Table S1: Climate finance studies highlighted in grey

Author	Date	Finance included in the study	Title	Approach, Content & Key Findings	Relevance
Isaac Akomea-Frimpong , David Adeabah, Deborah Ofosu & Emmanuel Junior Tenakwah	2021	Y	A review of studies on green finance of banks, research gaps and future directions	Content analysis approach used to critically analyse and summarize forty-six (46) relevant studies. The results found green securities, green investments, climate finance, carbon finance, green insurance, green credit and green infrastructural bonds as part of key green finance products of banks.	Green finance
Nalau, & Brodie	2021	N	Mapping the evolution and current trends in climate change adaptation science	A systematic literature reviews to analyse particular themes within the rapidly growing field of research, there is still missing an overall analysis of the current state of climate change adaptation science literature and its evolution. Multifaceted bibliometric review of climate change adaptation science literature focused on the human dimensions and how it has been constructed across time, disciplines, social relationships and geographies. The review, spans from 1978 to mid-2020. The results show an annual average increase of 28.5% in climate change adaptation publications, with over 26,000 authors publishing on this topic, and increasing diversity in publishing sources. Priority research topics and themes have been dynamic over time, while some core concepts (vulnerability, resilience, adaptive capacity) and sectors (water, agriculture) have remained relatively stable. Finance was missing from the priority topics. The key challenge going forward is how to consolidate this vast research endeavour into a more coherent adaptation theory.	Climate change adaptation science
Bhandary et al.	2021	Y	Climate finance policy in practice : a review of the evidence	Covers coastal flood risk reduction (CFRR) funding challenges. Found little research comparing multilevel arrangements across countries, and in particular exploring the performance of public funding arrangements for providing coastal flood risk reduction. Applied fiscal federalism to develop a multilevel governance analysis of public decision-making and fiscal authorities for CFRR in the Netherlands, Germany, the UK and Australia. The work locates key decision-making and fiscal authorities in multilevel governance arrangements and analyse their alignment with the benefits of CFRR measures (spill overs). Finds major fiscal redistributions may be put under pressure by rising costs likely under SLR and future coastal development and find that both fully and moderately decentralised arrangements may require greater central support for alternative measures, such as retreat, in light of growing financial burdens on local governments.	Coastal flood risk reduction (CFRR) funding
Bisaro et al.	2020	Y	Multilevel governance of coastal flood risk reduction : A public finance perspective	Review of literatures on coastal adaptation finance and on financial arrangements involving both public actors and private investors. Describes key actors and interests and identifies coastal financial arrangements that align public actor and private investor interests, finding that private provisioning, public-private Partnerships (PPP), and public debt arrangements are most promising. Uses empirical examples of adaptation. Found little evidence of institutional investment through public debt instruments. A number of policy instruments: concessional loans, tax incentives, and standards, may address this gap and enhance private coastal adaptation investment.	Coastal climate change adaptation financing
Hafner et al.	2020	Y	Closing the green finance gap – A systems perspective	A systematic review of the relevant academic literature published since 2009- 3357 articles from the Web of Science database and 2049 additional academic articles and studies from the Scopus database. 73 academic articles in total were analysed. This builds on the earlier scoping review as presented in Hafner et al. (2019) but includes a further database of articles and snowball process as described here to ensure a systematic review of literature. he work found barriers form a complex system characterised by path-dependency, lock-in and non-linearity. Systems theory as an	Green finance

				analytical framework is recommended to inform the related policy debate and authors propose the expansion or development of sustainable investment vehicles.	
Dedekorkut-Howes, Ayşın Torabi, Elnaz Howes, Michael	2020	Y	When the tide gets high: a review of adaptive responses to sea level rise and coastal flooding	This paper is a systematic literature review that identifies coastal flooding and sea level rise adaptation practices and evaluates their comparative advantages and disadvantages. 1,736 records were identified in search strings in Google Scholar and Scopus databases combined two sets of concepts: 1) practices, strategies, measures, actions, approaches; and 2) coastal flooding, storm surge, sea level rise. 119 relevant articles included in the quantitative review. The findings identify a major knowledge gap in comparative costs and benefits of alternative adaptation strategies and indicate that coastal climate adaptation needs to be tailored to local characteristics and use a combination of different structural and non-structural measures to be effective.	Climate change adaptation
Gigi Owen	2020	Y	What makes climate change adaptation effective? A systematic review of the literature	Through a systematic review of research literature, The Web of Knowledge was used to find articles published since the IPCC 4th Assessment Report (2007–2018) that included variations of the following terms: climate, change, adapt, success, effective, evaluate, monitor, indicator, and metric. These searches resulted in 3069 articles, 110 adaptation cases/initiatives were categorized that have been implemented and shown some degree of effectiveness. the ways in which these activities have been documented as effective is analysed using five indicators: reducing risk and vulnerability, developing resilient social systems, improving the environment, increasing economic resources, and enhancing governance and institutions. The paper takes stock of adaptation initiatives in practice and presents a snapshot of effectiveness, offering insight on what constitutes current adaptation practices, effectiveness, and emerging research gaps.	Climate change adaptation
Biesbroek, Robbert Delaney, Aogan	2020	N	Mapping the evidence of climate change adaptation policy instruments in Europe	Academic scholarship on climate change adaptation policy instruments in Europe is mapped using systematic approaches, 184 relevant articles published 2014–2019 are identified. Findings show that research is heavily concentrated on a limited number of western-European countries, with hardly any insights from eastern Europe and smaller countries. Most studies do not connect climate change impacts and risks with policy instruments, making assessment of policy effectiveness difficult, if not impossible.	Climate change adaptation
Sarah Hafner, Olivia James and Aled Jones	2019	Y	A Scoping Review of Barriers to Investment in Climate Change Solutions	A review of 91 academic papers to explore the barriers to investment in renewable energy infrastructure. The scoping review uses content analysis as derived from a set of 31 practice-based reports, published after the United Nations 15th Conference of the Parties (COP15) in Copenhagen in 2009, by leading networks, groups, or think tanks that represent the investment community. The key barriers identified. These may be linked to the immaturity of the market; however, it also highlights that there is a need for better communication between the three communities - policy, academia and investors. An important disconnect was found between academic research and practice-based reports and, in particular, areas of identified barriers by the investment community, such as technology risk, benchmarking, market liquidity, fossil fuel subsidies, fiduciary duty, and credit rating, are less well covered in the academic literature.	Barriers and climate solutions
Krogstrup, Signe Oman, William	2019	Y	Macroeconomic and Financial Policies for Climate Change Mitigation: A Review of the Literature	The practitioner paper provides an overview of the literature on the role of macroeconomic and financial policy tools in enabling transition. The literature provides a menu of policy tools for mitigation. A key conclusion is that fiscal tools are first in line and central but can and may need to be complemented by financial and monetary policy instruments.	Financial Policies - Climate Change Mitigation:
Holman, Ian P. Brown, Calum Carter, Timothy R. Harrison, Paula A. Rounsevell, Mark	2019	N	Improving the representation of adaptation in climate change impact models	This paper reviews the scientific literature to investigate conceptualisations and models of climate change adaptation, and the ways in which representation of adaptation in models can be improved. The review shows that real-world adaptive responses can be differentiated along a number of dimensions including intent or purpose, timescale, spatial scale, beneficiaries and providers, type of action, and sector.	Climate change science
Biesbroek, Robbert Berrang-ford, Lea Ford, James D Tanabe, Andrew	2018	N	Data, concepts and methods for large- n comparative climate change adaptation policy research: A systematic literature review	This article systematically captures and assesses the current state of larger-n ($n \geq 20$ cases) comparative adaptation policy literature. It systematically analyses 72 peer-reviewed articles to identify the key choices and challenges authors face when conducting their research. It is found scholars struggle to disentangle rhetoric from reality in adaptation, and very few studies engage in critical reflection of their conceptual, data and methodological choices	Climate change adaptation

				and the implications for their findings. It is concluded that efforts to increase data availability and use of more rigorous methodologies are necessary to advance comparative adaptation.	
Hu, Feng Wei, Haibo	2018	Y	An Empirical Study of Green Finance Research Through Bibliometrics	The authors conducted a bibliometric analysis from the Web of Science over the period of 1998–2017. Co-word analysis and co-citation analysis are employed to explore institution distribution, journal co-citation analysis, author co-citation analysis, document co-citation analysis, and keyword co-word analysis, particularly in high frequency items, intellectual turning points, burst points, and emerging trends. The Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, Google Scholar (GS), and PubMed (Chaomei Chen, 2017) were used. - 6644 appropriate journal articles were found. The landscape of green finance research is presented through bibliometrics. Co-word analysis and co-citation analysis were applied to detect discipline distribution, institution distribution, important journals, pioneer authors, milestone documents, and current research hotspots in green finance. The outstanding contributive disciplines to the development of green finance research are Environmental Sciences, followed by Energy Fuels, Environmental Studies, Economics, and Green Sustainable Science Technology.	Green finance
Runhaar, Hens Wilk, Bettina Persson, Åsa Uittenbroek, Caroline Wamsler, Christine	2018	N	Mainstreaming climate adaptation: taking stock about “what works” from empirical research worldwide	This paper takes stock of peer-reviewed empirical analyses of climate adaptation mainstreaming, in order to assess current achievements and identify the critical factors that render mainstreaming effective. The papers, selected from the Scopus database (end 2016), reported on 140 cases of mainstreaming practices. The results show that although in most cases adaptation policy outputs are identified, only in a minority of cases this translates into policy outcomes. This “implementation gap” is most strongly seen in developing countries.	Climate change adaptation
Diaz-Rainey, Ivan Robertson, Becky Wilson, Charlie	2017	Y	Stranded research? Leading finance journals are silent on climate change	This paper systematically analyses the content of 20,725 articles published in the leading 21 finance journals between January 1998 and June 2015. It found that only 12 (0.06%) are related in some way to climate finance. The three elite finance journals (Journal of Finance, Journal of Financial Economics and Review of Financial Studies) did not publish a single article related to climate finance over the 17.5-year period. In the 29 elite business journals spanning accounting, economics, management, marketing and operations research, as well as finance a similar dearth of published climate finance research is found. Explanations for this failure include methodological constraints and editorial policies.	climate finance

Source: Author’s empirical analysis & data

Note to Table S1: References are listed in S5

Supplementary File S2: Large-n Comparative Case

Table S3: Overview of large-n comparative city case studies (12 (5-US, 4- EU, 3- Global))

Study	Date	Article Title	Region	Finance covered in the study	Scope	Findings, Barriers & Recommendations
Einstein et al.	2020	Can Mayors Lead on Climate Change ? Evidence from Six Years of Surveys	US	N	Leadership on climate change 600 US Mayors Mitigation focused	Leadership on climate change requires aggressive policy actions Land use and local transportation policy reform remain promising–though challenging
Reckien, D	2019	Dedicated versus mainstreaming approaches in local climate plans (LCP) in Europe -	EU	N	Mainstreaming approaches LCP 885 cities across European countries <i>UA</i> <i>“core cities” of the EU-28</i>	Mainstreaming is low for adaptation (10% of cities; 29% of plans) 10% of the EU cities have mainstreamed adaptation plan, 29% adaptation LCPs regarded as mainstreamed LCPs are less common in Southern Europe. Northern European cities are pioneers in local climate adaptation, (more experience of climate events, such as flooding) Approximately x3 the number of local authorities that plan for adaptation than those that plan for mitigation choose a mainstreaming approach (12% of mitigation plans are mainstreamed; 29% of adaptation plans are mainstreamed). Adaptation is (more than mitigation) understood as a local, multi-dimensional. Horizontal mainstreaming is major effort - pay off is not guaranteed. Dedicated LCP in parallel to a mainstreamed plan (joint or subsequent “dual track approach”) is most successful
Lesnikowski, Ford, Berrang-Ford, Biesbroek, Berrang-Ford,	2019	A policy mixes approach to conceptualizing and measuring climate change adaptation (CCAP) policy	Global	N	Policy mixes approach to CCAP 125 local governments located in 5 countries, Canada, France, Germany, the Netherlands & UK 3328 policy instruments	Of 125 local government only six demonstrated no textual evidence of adaptation policy instrument adoption. All in Germany or the Netherlands. UK local governments adopt the largest & the Netherlands lowest number. Structured differences between countries in approach to adaptation policy design Local governments policy goals address multitude climate risks, hundreds of individual policy instruments. Stronger emphasis on strategic planning and organizational development among local governments in the UK and on direct expenditures in the Netherlands Research gap: More nuanced measurements of adaptation policy that capture the diversity of policy instruments and policy goals
Moser, S C. Ekstrom, J A. Kim, J Heitsch, S	2019	Adaptation finance archetypes: local governments’ persistent challenges of funding adaptation to climate change and ways to overcome them	US	Y	Understanding of adaptation finance challenges: archetype analysis 173 valid survey responses from 540 local California. Local governments representatives	Persistent lack of funding acts as the key adaptation barrier. Patterns interrelated causal factors/traits/outcomes from gaining attention (and funding) to acquiring, using, and managing adaptation finance. Fifteen archetypal adaptation finance challenges Seven focal points for adaptation finance challenges (capability and ability): risk, funding need, financial standing, funding providers, types of funding/finance, funding mechanisms and administering funds. Saw as most important (3):establish adaptation as a priority, make economic case, build capacity funding seeker. Not anyone actor, local, state, federal, philanthropic, or private, can make sufficient progress alone. Not any one archetype alone, i.e., no “silver bullet” solution, will address deep-seated finance challenges, “ <i>simply providing more funding</i> ”, critical, but inadequate by itself .

						Key: heed special caution with “solutions” that reinforce long-standing injustices/disparities, innovative funding mechanisms & private sector actors in adaptation arena can aggravate difficult/complex problem for others.
Reckien et al.	2018	How are cities planning to respond to climate change? Assessment of local climate plans from 885 cities in the EU	EU	N	Local planning of climate mitigation and adaptation plans 885 cities in the EU	Mitigation plans are more numerous than adaptation plans. City size/national legislation/international networks influence the development of local climate plans, size matters-80% cities >500,000 inhabitants have comprehensive/stand-alone mitigation and/or adaptation plan Cities in 4, i.e., Denmark/France/Slovakia/United Kingdom, twice as likely to produce local mitigation plans & x5 likely to produce local adaptation plans, as countries with national climate legislation. The integration adaptation & mitigation is country-specific - observed in 2 countries (France/UK) where compulsory local climate plans. Local climate plans produced for international climate networks found many countries where autonomous plans are less common. EU Covenant of Mayors important role to play encouraging smaller cities. Research gaps: Factors contribute the most to adaptation planning & how interact each other & other factors.
Stults &- Woodruff	2017	Looking under the hood of local adaptation plans: shedding light on the action’s priority	US	Y	Local Adaptation Plan (LAP) quality assessment 44 stand alone, local adaptation plans in the USA	Numerous and varied actions included in adaptation plans . Some types of actions, such as building codes and advocacy not widely used. Twenty-eight out of the 43 plans (66%) linked actions to possible future climate impacts. Plans rarely contain significant details about how actions implemented, rarely/unevenly connect adaptation actions to the specific climate-related impacts they address. Plans perform poorly on all the implementation and monitoring metrics. Most plans emphasize mainstreaming. Limited details about actions, co-benefits and cost, not fully considered actions feasibility/effectiveness. Missing details reflect plans still in early stages of the adaptation cycle. Weak implementation guidance limits translation of plans into action. Research gaps: Engaging stakeholders on what adaptation actions get implemented, why/how of effective implemented actions, quantitative/qualitative & evaluation metrics.
Aguiar, Bentz, Silva, Fonseca, Swart, Santos, Penha-Lopes	2017	Adaptation to climate change at local level in Europe: An overview	EU	Y	Triggers and barriers, climate risks tackled and adaptation funding 147 Local Adaptation Strategies in Europe.	No archetypical way of planning for adaptation. Main barrier to adaptation plans implementation are insufficient resources, capacity (mainly technical), commitment (mainly political) and uncertainty, highlighting the dependence on external financial support in many cases. Although EU research networks (LIFE+) funds tackle some of these barriers. Public funding at local/national level is mainly enabling local adaptation. Differing patterns of adaptation planning & adaptive capacity identified among different regions in Europe. Large municipalities fund adaptation locally, international/national funds important for less urban territories. Triggers for a LAS were political e.g., implementation of EU policies or national commitments & national legislation to adapt to climate change, in France, Denmark, Hungary, and Ireland. Ninety-five out of the 147 LAS mention the existence of barriers to the implementation of adaptation options. Lack of human/financial resources was noted by most of LAS, more relevant in Southern Europe. Northern Europe municipalities reported uncertainty on climate change scenarios as an adaptation barrier. Mostly extreme climatic events, including floods/storms ,and then heatwaves/drought led to prioritising action.

						Adaptation planning in Europe mostly reactive, i.e., not significantly influenced by climate projections/impacts - institutional, socio-economic dimensions are important constraints for the implementation of adaptation plans.
Araos, Berrang-Ford, Ford, Austin, Biesbroek & Lesnikowski,	2016	Climate change adaptation planning in large cities: A systematic global assessment	Global	Y	Adaptation tracking - global assessments of adaptation taking place across cities 401 global CAPs for their level of maturity	61 cities (15%) report any adaptation initiatives, 73 cities (18%) report on planning towards adaptation policy. Classification: extensive adaptors, moderate adaptors, early-stage adaptors, and non-reporting. Extensive adaptors large cities located in North America, Europe, and Oceania adapting to variety impacts. Moderate adaptors address general DRR rather than specific impacts - mix developed /developing countries. Early-stage adaptors evidence of planning for adaptation, but do not report any initiatives. Urban adaptation in early stages, examples of government leadership all levels wealth/institutional barriers. Cities with extensive adaptation experience exhibit mix of policy types, direct and concrete activities - legislation changes & soft policies - capacity building and research. Problems disentangling lack of adaptation from lack of reporting, results likely bias findings. Most cities not reporting adaption planning. Some cities are innovating. Research gaps: Systematic study urban adaptation of global trends urban adaptation different countries
Shi, Chu, & Debats	2015	Explaining Progress in Climate Adaptation Planning Across 156 U.S. Municipalities	US	Y	Climate Adaptation Planning (CAP) progress assessment - (political leadership, fiscal and administrative resources for adaptation) 156 U.S. Municipalities	Leading adaptation cities -committed local elected officials, higher municipal expenditures per capita & climate awareness. State policies on climate adaptation not statistically significant predictor (policies not yet be strong enough). State governments opportunity to be catalyst action & integrate requirements for climate-risk evaluations into existing funding streams/investment. Local governments around the country are beginning to adapt. Cities developed diverse adaptation strategies, integrating into local land use and development plans, infrastructure design & construction regulations, ecosystems protection policies, emergency preparedness. Local governments have difficulties understanding climate science & altering planning practices. Cities with high adaptive capacity overcome barriers- possess administrative and financial resources, strong leadership, ability obtain/communicate climate information & cultural values support institutional responses & strong state policies plans. Regional planning entity's role in exchange of information, pooling & channelling resources, technical assistance Research gaps: Factors help planners implement adaptation & conditions implementation results in outcomes.
Heidrich, Dawson, Reckien, & Walsh	2013	Assessment of the climate preparedness of 30 urban areas in the UK	UK	N	Adaptation & mitigation action across the UK 30 UK urban areas	All areas acknowledge climate change as threat & adaptation/mitigation planning required. Two urban areas did not have official adaptation or mitigation plans. Typically, mitigation activities across all cities were more advanced than adaptation plans. Variability across adaptation plans. A combination of incentives and regulation stimulate more comprehensive strategies and action.
Hanson, Nicholls, Ranger, Hallegatte, Corfee-Morlot, Herweijer, Chateau	2011	A global ranking of port cities with high exposure to climate extremes	Global	Y	World's large port cities (population exceeding one million inhabitants in 2005) to coastal flooding due to sea-level rise and storm surge now and in the 2070 36 port cities across the globe	Total value of exposed assets (2005) all cities estimated USD\$3,000 billion; 5% of global GDP in with USA/Japan /Netherlands with the highest values. By the 2070s, total population exposed grow >x3 due to the combined effects of sea-level rise, subsidence, population growth & urbanisation, >10x than ten times current levels or approximately 9% of projected global GD<P.. Population growth, socio-economic growth and urbanization factors.

						<p>Exposure concentrated in a few cities: collectively Asia dominates population exposure now and, in the future.</p> <p>High potential benefits from risk-reduction planning/policies at the city scale.</p> <p>Research gaps: Prediction of protection costs for cities, circumventing the lack of comprehensive data on past investments in coastal flood protection, assessment of the nature of the local risks & costs and benefits of adaptation. Research to facilitate the development of risk sharing approaches/insurance markets. Independent or integrated assessment for other aspects climate change, investigation of the influence of coastal defences on exposure & desire for their construction, affordability of adaptation measures & willingness to pay for these.</p>
Bassett & Shandas	2010	Innovation and climate action planning: Perspectives from municipal plans	US	N	<p>Innovation in climate action planning study</p> <p>20 US City CAPs</p>	<p>Great diversity in what constitutes a CAP, some are motivational documents, others are extremely detailed implementation plans with concrete goals, clear objectives, and well-reasoned methods. Decision to prepare a CAP reflects the existence of local political will/leadership.</p> <p>CAPs rely heavily on well-known land use and transportation solutions to the climate challenge - enhanced transit, compact community design & green building codes.</p> <p>CAPs highly visible actions (e.g., tree planting) producing immediate results (e.g., energy or cost savings from weatherization).</p> <p>Planned actions may be considered innovative, but many are traditional planning strategies tied to long-range & current planning operations of cities.</p> <p>CAPs special-purpose plans, planning departments not central to plan, mainstreaming is needed.</p>

Source: Author's empirical analysis & data

Note to Table S2: References are listed in S6.

Supplementary File S3: Detailed description of the five research topic from keyword clusters

Detailed description of the five research topic clusters (obtained from the keyword analysis in VOSViewer)

Keywords chosen by authors highlight the core focus of publications and denote research topics. Keywords across this literature are clustered using VOSviewer software, and cross checked in NVIVO, to extract the most common research topics. Five research topic clusters are found namely, climate finance, insurance, adaptation planning, resilience and climate hazards. Key literature relating to each cluster (see Table S2) is analysed in detail and forms a core research output for this study.

Research in Theme One: Climate Finance assesses climate finance, capital, markets and investment (Bayulgen, 2020; Hallegatte, Henriët & Corfee-morlot, 2011; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Mazzucato & Penna, 2016). Topics such as transition (Bayulgen, 2020; Cheung & Oßenbrügge, 2020; Morone & Sica, 2018; Semieniuk et al., 2020) dominate this field. A key focus of this research cluster is the low carbon economy, energy, and renewable energy (Griffiths & Sovacool, 2020; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Gibbs & While 2011; Peng & Bai, 2020;). The use of instruments is a key component (Basak & Werf, 2019; Banhalmi-Zakar et al., 2016; Brown, Biesbroek et al., 2014; Collier et al., 2021). A strong focus in this literature stream is the efforts to achieve the (low carbon) transition (Sureshkumar, 2011), as well as climate finance, green finance, and green bonds (Akomea-frimpong et al., 2011; Ameli et al., 2020; Christophers, Bigger & Johnson, 2020;). This research also covers cost, the role of the investors and pension funds. System wide issues are also covered such as the market as well economy and the role of banks. This area has grown prominently in importance in recent year, 2018-2019. As would be expected there are strong links to the private sector and adaptation finance and climate finance in Cluster Three (Actors) (Yellow). The growth in green finance studies since 2017 is demonstrated in this Theme Two: Climate Finance key word cluster.

Theme Two: Insurance is smaller theme and covers insurance, loss and damage (Bettini, Gioli & Felli, 2020; Collier et al., 2021; Collier & Cox, 2021; Han & Peng, 2021; Thistlethwaite, 2012; Tonn et al.; 2021). Climate transformation features in some of this research (Hölscher, 2019; Termeer et al., 2017).

Theme three: Adaptation Planning is centred around the concept of climate adaptation planning (Aaros et al., 2016; Aguiar et al, 2018; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Olazabal et al., 2019; Owen, 2021; Reckien et al., 2018;) which is often researched in conjunction with mitigation and resilience to climate change (Bears & Zolnikov; Collier & Cox, 2021). Several aspects of adaptation planning are covered (Henstra, 2017; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Maor, Tosun & Jordon, 2017; Olazabal et al., 2019). Assessing the integration of adaptation planning (Runhaar et al., 2018;) and the role of decision-makers in society (Argyriou, Fleming & Wright, 2012), as too international drivers such as the Paris Agreement and the UNFCCC (Lesnikowski et al., 2017;) all received considerable attention. The role of networks in climate change adaptation has been an area of focus (Bednar, Henstra & Mcbean, 2019; Jordon & Johnson, 2018;). There are strong links to how this relates to Theme Four (Yellow) and hazards such as flooding and sea level rise.

Theme Four: Resilience covers resilience to climate change (Bears & Zolnikov; Collier & Cox, 2021; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Lade, Walker & Haider, 2020; Stults & Woodruff, 2017) and related terms such as capacity and sustainability. There are strong links to community and the challenge of resources for adaptation planning.

Theme Five: Climate Hazards is a smaller area and is centred around hazard/risk, weather and exposure (Christophers, Bigger & Johnson, 2020; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Stoner, 2012) and the links to disaster risk reduction (Aakre et al., 2010; Begum et al., 2014; Bouwer & Aerts, 2006; Torabi et al., 2016). These areas are often researched in conjunction with coastal areas, flood, and sea level rise (Hallegatte et al., 2011; Torabi, Dedekorkut-Howes & Howes, 2018) because of the pronounced vulnerability related to these locations and hazards. The private sector features in this literature (Pauw et al., 2016 ;

Tompkins & Eakin, 2012; Thistlethwaite, 2012) as too are references to the role of the public sector (Biesbroek & Peters, 2018; Castan, 2017; Hamin, Gurrán & Emlinger, 2014; Heidrich et al. 2013) are often the focus of research because of their pronounced vulnerability to climate change. Research covering retreat of communities and assets out of exposed areas) also featured. This is a highly dispersed scholarly field with no tight grouping of common themes or scholars, there are strong links to many of the other themes from this area, as a result it is difficult to pinpoint and examine separately. This is the area where most of the literature can be found which specifically details investment in urban adaptation, the focus of this paper. This and other research cluster encompasses a diverse range of research on actors and authorities/agents in the adaptation and climate finance processes (Birchall & Bonnett, 2020; Heijden, 2018; Kalinowski, 2021). The focus of this cluster is on both the public sector and private sector as well as decision-makers (Hjerpe & Storbjo, 2015, Picketts, 2018) and the role they have in the development of climate adaptation strategies (Aguiar et al., 2018; Bassett & Shandas, 2010; Carter, 2011; Chen et al., 2015). There are strong links to value and responsibility which both feature in this research area. Discourse, influence and decision-making processes and their influence in the development of adaptation strategies all feature. Community and concepts such as adaptive capacity are also elements in this research.

Note: References are listed in S5.

Table S3: Keyword clusters and key literature (author analysis VOSViewer and NVIVO)

Cluster	Sub Theme	References
Climate Finance	Banks	Akomea-Frimpong et al. 2021, Bolton et al. 2020, CCFLA, 2021, CCFLA 2020, Geddes, et al, 2020, Gianfrate & Peri, 2019, Gunningham, 2020, Hafner et al, 2019, Keenan, Chu & Peterson, 2019, Mazzucato & Penna, 2016, Pauw, 2016, Pereira, 2021, Svartzman et al. 2020
	Climate finance, capital, markets and investment	Bayulgen, 2020; Hallegatte, Henriët & Corfee-morlot, 2011; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Mazzucato & Penna, 2016; Meckling & Jenner, 2016; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Ng, 2018; Pereira, 2021; Svartzman et al., 2021
	Climate finance/ green finance/ green bonds	Akomea-frimpong et al., 2011; Ameli et al., 2020; Chander et al., 2019; Christophers, Bigger & Johnson, 2020; Hafner et al., 2020; 2019; Hourcade, Perrissin & Rozenberg, 2012; Kavvadia, 2021; Maltais & Nykvist, 2020; Pereira, 2021; Ng, 2018; Sartzetakis, 2020
	Climate transformation	Hölscher, 2019; Termeer et al., 2017; Zang et al., 2018; Zanotti et al., 2020.
	Cost	Bhandary et al., 2020; Fankhauser & Soare, 2013; Kotchen & Costello, 2011; Mathew et al., 2011; Mullin, Smith & Mcnamara,2019; Peng & Bai, 2020; Reguero et al., 2020; Soto-Montes-de-Oca, Bark & González-Arellano,2020; Ware & Bahalmi-zakar, 2020).
	Economy	Bayulgen, 2020; Hallegatte, Henriët & Corfee-morlot, 2011; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Mazzucato & Penna, 2016; Meckling & Jenner, 2016; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Ng, 2018; Pereira, 2021; Svartzman et al., 2021
	Energy, and renewable energy	Jakob et al., 2016; Leiren, Inderberg & Rayner, 2020; Mazzucato, & Semieniuk, 2018
	Low carbon economy	Ameli, 2020; Bolton & Foxton, 2015; Bridge et al., 2019; Griffiths & Sovacool, 2020; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Jonas et al., 2011; Peng & Bai, 2020; Polzin & Sanders,2020; Sartzetakis, 2020; Semieniuk et al., 2020; Sureshkumar, 2011
	Instruments	Basak & Werf, 2019; Bahalmi-Zakar et al., 2016; Brown, Sorrell & Kivimaa, 2019; Biesbroek et al.,2014; Collier et al., 2021; Katz & Noring, 2020; Reguero et al., 2020; Roberts et al., 2017; Wang & Lea, 2016
	Investors/pension funds	Adhikari, Shaila & Chalkasra, 2021; Alkhani, 2020; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Pauw et al., 2016
	Market	Bayulgen, 2020; Hallegatte, Henriët & Corfee-morlot, 2011; Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Mazzucato & Penna, 2016; Meckling & Jenner, 2016; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Ng, 2018; Pereira, 2021; Svartzman et al., 2021
Transition	Bayulgen,2020; Cheung, O Benbrügge, 2020; Morone & Sica, 2018; Hafner et al., 2020; Huitema et al., 2017; Maestosi, Andreucci & Civiero, 2021; Romero-Lankao & Dodman, 2011; Polzin & Sanders,2020; Peng & Bai, 2020; Sartzetakis, 2020; Semieniuk et al., 2020	
Insurance	Justice	Parks & Roberts , 2010
	Loss/Damage & Insurance	Bettini, Gioli & Felli, 2020; Collier et al., 2021; Collier & Cox, 2021; Han & Peng, 2021; Jarzabkowski, Chalkias & Clarke, 2019; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Porrini & Schwarze, 2014; Regueroa et al., 2020; Soto-Montes-de-Oca, Bark & González-Arellano,2020; Thistlethwaite, 2012; Tonn et al., 2021.
	Uncertainty	Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Tennekes et al., 2014
Adaptation Planning	Adaptation planning	Adam, Steinebach & Knill, 2018; Bednar, Henstra & McBean, 2019; Biesboek & Delaney 2020; Castan, 2017; Ford & King, 2015; Heijden, 2018; Haasnott & Biesboek 2020, Hallegatte, 2008; Heijden, Picketts, 2018; Henstra, 2017; Henstra, 2016; Leck & Roberts, 2015; Lee & Painter, 2015; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Maor, Tosun & Jordon , 2017; Maor at al., 2019; Nalau & Verrall, 2020; Olazabal et al., 2019; Reckien et al., 2019 ; Root et al, 2016; Wright & Nyberg, 2017
	Climate adaptation planning	Aaros et al., 2016; Aguiar et al., 2018; Alves et al., 2020; Baker et al., 2012; Biesbroek et al., 2018; Birkmann et al., 2010; Hangar et al., 2015; Hanson et al.; 2011; Howlett & Kemmerling, 2017; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Olazabal et al., 2019; Owen, 2021; Reckien et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2015; Stults & Woodruff, 2017
	Climate resilience	Bears & Zolnikov; Collier & Cox, 2021; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Lade, Walker & Haider, 2020; Stults & Woodruff, 201).
	Decision-makers	Argyriou, Fleming & Wright, 2012, Bassett & Shandas, 2010;Berrang Ford et al., 2019; Beisbroek et al., 2018; Eckersley, England & Ferry , 2018; Keskitalo, Preston & Howlett, 2019; Lamphere & Shefner, 2018; Lehmann et al., 2015; Lund, 2018; McConnell & Greal & Lea, 2020; Ostrom, 2010; Patterson & Huitema, 2019; Reckien & Petkova, 2019; Root et al., 2016; Tennekes et al., 2014
	Integration- adaptation planning	Hanger et al., 2015; Reckien, 2019; Runhaar et al., 2018; Scoville-Simonds, Jamali & Hufty, 2020; Widner, 2018
	Mitigation	Abadie, Galarraga & Rübhelke, 2013, Ameli & Kammen, 2012, Cheung & O Benbrügge, 2020,, Einecker & Kirby, 2020, Ford & Berrang-Ford, 2016, Grafakos et al. 2015, Haasnoot et al, 2020, Hafner et al, 2019, Keenan, Chu & Peterson 2019, Keeley & Managi, Miller & Swann, 2019, Krogstrup & Oman, 2019, Nguyen, Davidson & Gleeson, 2019, Rashidi, Stadelmann & Patt, 2019, Romero-Lankao & Dodman, 2011, Tolliver, 2019, Wright & Nyberg, 2017,, Ye et al, 2021
	Networks	Bednar, Henstra & Mcbean, 2019; Dzebo, 2019, Fu, 2015; Jordon & Johnson, 2018;
Paris Agreement & UNFCC	Bertoldi et al., 2018; Lesnikowski et al., 2017; Oberlack & Eisenack, 2014; Reckien et al., 2018; Tolliver et al., 2019	
Resilience	Climate resilience	Bears & Zolnikov; Collier & Cox, 2021; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Lade, Walker & Haider, 2020; Stults & Woodruff, 201

	Capacity	Howlett, 2013, Coaffee et al, 2018, Taylor & Harman, 2016, Lesnikowski, Biesbroek, Ford & Berrang- Ford, 220, Stults & Woodruff,2017, Tuler et al., 2020, Williams, 2020,
	Sustainability	Eckersley, England & Ferry, 2019
	Community	Howlett, 2013, Coaffee et al, 2018, Taylor & Harman, 2016, Lesnikowski, Biesbroek, Ford & Berrang- Ford, 220, Schlosberg, Collins & Niemeyer, 2017, Stults & Woodruff,2017, Torabi, Dedekorkut-Howes & Howes, 2018, Tuler, Webler, 2020, Williams, 2020,
	Resources for adaptation	Aaros et al., 2016, Adam, Steinebach & Knill, 2018; Aguiar et al, 2018; Alves et al., 2020; Baker et al.2012; Bednar, Henstra & McBean, 2019; Biesboek & Delaney, 2020, Biesbroek et al., 2018; Birkmann et al., 2010; Castan, 2017, Ford & King, 2015, Hangar et al., 2015; Haasnott & Biesboek 2020, Hallegatte, 2008, Hanson et al.; 2011; Heijden, Picketts, 2018; Henstra, 2017; Henstra, 2016; Heijden, 2018, Howlett & Kemmerling, 2017; Leck & Roberts, 2015; Lee & Painter, 2015; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Maor, Tosun & Jordon , 2017; Maor at al., 2019; Nalau & Verrall, 2020; Olazabal et al., 2019; Owen, 2021; Reckien et al., 2018; Root et al., 2016, Shi et al., 2015; Stults & Woodruff, 2017,Wright & Nyberg, 2017
Climate Hazards	Adaptive capacity	Ford & King, 2015, Fünfgeld et al., 2019, Ford et al. 2013, Nalau & Verrall, 2021, Ninan & Inoue, 2016, Patterson & Huitema, 2019, Rashidi et al., 2019, Revi et al., 2014, Wellstead et al. 2016, Williams, 2020, Zanotti, et al. 2020
	Actors/authorities	Basak & Werf, 2019; Birchall & Bonnett, 2020; Han & Peng 2019; Heijden, 2018;; Jordan & Huietma, 2014; Kalinowski, 2021; Lee & Painter, 2015; Torabi, Dedekorkut-Howes & Howes, 2018
	Adaptation strategies	Aguiar et al., 2018; Bassett & Shandas, 2010; Carter, 2011; Chen et al., 2015; Hamin, Gurran & Emlinger, 2014; Henstra, 2018; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Lee & Painter, 2015; Little et al., 2015; Lui & Jensen, 2017; Moser et al., 2019 Picketts, 2018; Sainz et al., 2021; Scoville-Simonds, Jamali & Hufty, 2020; Olazabal et al., 2019; Stults & Woodruff, 2018; Tuler, Dow & Webler, 2020; Ware & Banhalmi-zakar, 2020
	Business/ private investment	Adhikari, Shaila & Chalkasra, 2021; Alkhani, 2020; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Pauw et al., 2016
	Climate transformation	Hölscher, 2019; Termeer et al., 2017; Zang et al., 2018; Zanotti et al., 2020.
	Coastal areas, flood/sea level rise	Hallegatte et al., 2011; Hamin, Gurran & Emlinger, 2014; Heidrick et al., 2021; Torabi, Dedekorkut-Howes & Howes, 2018
	Conflicts	Biesbroek et al., 2014; Geddes et al., 2020; Rasmussen et al., 2020; Rempel & Gupta, 2020
	Community	Ditto above
	Discourse/influence/ decision-making	Castan, 2017; Eriksen, Nightingale & Eakin, 2018; Gheddes et al., 2020; Nalau, Preston &Maloney, 2015; Oberlack & Eisenack, 2014; Schlosberg, Collins & Niemeyer, 2017, Wittneben, Banerjee & Levy, 2012; Zhang et al., 2018
	Decision-makers	Hjerpe & Storbjo, 2015, Picketts, 2018)
	Disaster risk reduction	Aakre et al., 2010; Begum et al., 2014; Bouwer & Aerts, 2006; Collier & Cox, 2021; Huq et al., 2007; Helmer & Hihurst, 2006; Islam et al., 2021; Kelman, Gaillard & Mercer,2015; Little et al., 2015; Lucas & Booth, 2020, Singh et al., 2020; Torabi et al., 2016
	Hazard/risk, weather/exposure	Christophers, Bigger & Johnson, 2020; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Stoner, 2012
	Private sector	Adhikari, Shaila & Chalkasra, 2021; Alkhani, 2020; Klein et al., 2018; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Pauw, 2018, Pauw et al., 2016 ; Tompkins & Eakin, 2012; Thistlethwaite, 201X)
	Public sector	Aakre et al., 2010, Bayulgen, 2020; Biesbroek & Peters, 2018; Castan, 2017; Hallegatte, Giordono, Boudet & Gard-Murray, 2015; Henriët & Corfee-morlot, 2011, Hamin, Gurran & Emlinger, 2014;Heidrich et al. 2013; Leck & Robert, 2015; Nguyen, Davidson & Gleeson, 2018; Mazzucato & Semieniuk, 2017, Patterson & Huitema, 2019
	Responsibility	Castan, 2017; Eriksen, Nightingale & Eakin, 2018; Gheddes et al., 2020; Nalau, Preston &Maloney, 2015; Oberlack & Eisenack, 2014; Schlosberg, Collins & Niemeyer, 2017, Wittneben, Banerjee & Levy, 2012; Zhang et al., 2018
Uncertainty	Hafner, James & Jones, 2019; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Tennekes et al., 2014	
Value	Barrage, 2017; Brown, Sorrell & Kivimaa, 2019; Corfee-Morlot et al., 2011; Kotchen & Costello, 2018; Lund, 2018; Rogers, 2019; Soto-Montes-de-Oca, Bark & González-Arellano,2020	
Vulnerability	Kelman, Gaillard & Mercer, 2015; Schlosberg, Collins & Niemeyer, 2017	

Source: Author's empirical analysis & data

Note to Table S2: References are listed in S6

Supplementary File S5: Citation and co-citation

Figure S5 Co-citation analysis with date overlay (VOSViewer)

<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Source Title</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Average/Year</i>
<i>Financing renewable energy: Who is financing what and why it matter?</i>	Mazzucato, M and Semieniuk, G	Climatic Change	2018	171	34,2
<i>Will COVID-19 fiscal recovery packages accelerate or retard progress on climate change?</i>	Hepburn et al.	Oxford Review Of Economic Policy	2020	156	52
<i>The role of green finance in environmental protection: Two aspects of market mechanism and policies</i>	Wang, Y; Zhi, Q	Clean Energy for Clean City: CUE 2016 - Applied Energy Symposium/Forum:	2016	96	13,7 1
<i>Beyond market failures: the market creating and shaping roles of state investment banks</i>	Mazzucato, M and Penna C	Journal of Economic Policy Reform	2016	84	12
<i>The green advantage: Exploring the convenience green bonds</i>	Gianfrate, G; Peri, M	Journal Of Cleaner Production	2019	70	17,5
<i>Financing climate change adaptation</i>	Bouwer, LM; Aerts, JCJH	Disasters	2006	61	3,59
<i>Paying to save the beach: effects of local finance decisions on coastal management</i>	Mullin, M; Smith, MD and McNamara, DE	Climatic Change	2019	68	17
<i>A socio-technical perspective on low carbon investment challenges - Insights for UK energy policy</i>	Bolton, R and Foxon TJ	Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions	2015	63	7,88
<i>Financing climate change adaptation</i>	Bouwer AM and Aerts JC JH	Disasters	2006	61	3,59
<i>Investing in low carbon transition: Energy finance as an adaptive market</i>	Hall S , Foxton TJ & Bolton R	Climate Policy	2017	60	10
<i>Past performance and future needs for low carbon climate resilient infrastructure - An investment perspective</i>	Kennedy, C; Corfee-Morlot, J	Energy Policy	2013	54	5,4
<i>Fostering green investments and tackling climate-related financial risks: Which role for macroprudential policies?</i>	D'Orazio, P; Popoyan, L	Ecological Economics	2019	52	13
<i>Greening of the financial system and fuelling a sustainability transition A discursive approach to assess landscape pressures on the Italian financial system</i>	Falcone, P M; Morone, P; Sica, E	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	2018	49	9,8
<i>From sustainability accounting to a green financing system: Institutional legitimacy and market heterogeneity in a global financial centre</i>	Ng, Artie W.	Journal Of Cleaner Production	2018	46	9,2
<i>Not a panacea: private-sector engagement in adaptation and adaptation finance in developing countries</i>	Pauw, W. P.	Climate Policy	2015	39	4,88
<i>Stranded research: Leading journals are silent on climate change</i>	Diaz I, Robertson B & Wilson C	Climatic Change	2017	36	6
<i>Closing the green finance gap - A systems perspective</i>	Hafner, S; Jones, A; Anger-Kraavi, A; Pohl, J	Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions	2020	35	11,6 7
<i>Carbon Pricing Revenues Could Close Infrastructure Access Gaps</i>	Jakob, M; Chen, C; Fuss, S; Marxen, A; Rao, N D.; Edenhofer, O	World Development	2016	32	4,57
<i>Private finance for adaptation: do private realities meet public ambitions?</i>	Pauw, W. P.; Klein, R. J. T.; Vellinga, P.; Biermann, F.	Climatic Change	2016	31	4,43
<i>Climate Finance</i>	Hong, H; Karolyi, G. A; Scheinkman, J A.	Review Of Financial Studies	2020	31	10.3 3
<i>Low-carbon transition risks for finance</i>	Semieniuk; Campiglio, E; Mercure, J-F; Volz, Uh; Edwards, N R.	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews-Climate Change	2021	29	9,67
<i>Understanding green bonds in advancing sustainability</i>	Maltais, A; Nykvist, B	Journal Of Sustainable Finance & Investment	2021	28	9,33

<i>Environmental Beta or How Institutional Investors Think about Climate Change and Fossil Fuel Risk</i>	Christophers, Brett	Annals Of The American Association Of Geographers	2019	27	6,75
<i>Insurance models and European climate change policies: an assessment</i>	Porrini, Donatella; Schwarze, Reimund	European Journal Of Law And Economics	2014	26	2,89
<i>Worth the risk? An evaluation of alternative finance mechanisms for residential retrofit</i>	Brown, Donal; Sorrell, Steve; Kivimaa, Paula	Energy Policy	2019	25	6,25
<i>Varieties of market-based policy: Instrument choice in climate policy</i>	Meckling, Jonas; Jenner, Steffen	Environmental Politics	2016	23	3,29
<i>Mobilizing private finance for coastal adaptation: A literature review</i>	Bisaro, Alexander; Hinkel, Jochen	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews-Climate Change	2018	22	4,4
<i>How to finance the transition to low-carbon energy in Europe?</i>	Polzin, Friedemann; Sanders, Mark	Energy Policy	2020	21	7

Table S5A: Top twenty most cited articles climate finance (CF) articles only

(Source: WoS at 23/5/22)

Table S5B: Top 25 most cited articles (Core dataset of articles examining the financing of adaptation)

<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Source Title</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>To</i>	<i>Year</i>
				<i>tal</i>	
<i>A global ranking of port cities with high exposure to climate extremes</i>	Hanson et al.	Climatic Change	2011	37	31,2
<i>Financing renewable energy: Who is financing what and why it matter?</i>	Mazzucato, M and Semieniuk, G	Climatic Change	2018	17	34.2
<i>Will COVID-19 fiscal recovery packages accelerate or retard progress on climate change?</i>	Hepburn et al.	Oxford Review of Economic Policy	2020	15	52
<i>Managing private and public adaptation to climate change</i>	Tompkins, E L and Eakin, H	Global Environmental Change-Human and Policy Dimensions	2012	14	13,0
<i>Beyond market failures: the market creating and shaping roles of state investment banks</i>	Mazzucato, M and Penna C	Journal of Economic Policy Reform	2016	84	12
<i>Adaptation to climate change at local level in Europe: An overview</i>	Aguiar, FC; Bentz, J and Penha-Lopes, G	Environmental Science & Policy	2018	78	15.6
<i>Beyond state/non-state divides: Global cities and the governing of climate change</i>	Bulkeley, H and Schroeder, H	European Journal of International Relations	2012	66	6
<i>Legitimate adaptive flood risk governance beyond the dikes: the cases of Hamburg, Helsinki and Rotterdam</i>	Mees, HLP; Driessen, PPJ and Runhaar, HAC	Regional Environmental Change	2014	61	6,78
<i>Financing climate change adaptation</i>	Bouwer, LM and Aerts, JCJH	Disasters	2006	61	3,59
<i>Paying to save the beach: effects of local finance decisions on coastal management</i>	Mullin, M; Smith, MD and McNamara, DE	Climatic Change	2019	68	17
<i>Financing climate change adaptation</i>	Bouwer AM and Aerts JC JH	Disasters	2006	61	3,59
<i>What does the Paris Agreement mean for adaptation?</i>	Lesnikowski, A; Ford, J and Austin, SE	Climate Policy	2017	58	9,67
<i>Adapting or maladapting: Building resilience to climate-related disasters in coastal cities</i>	Torabi, E; Dedekorkut-Howes, A and Howes, M	Cities	2018	54	10,8
<i>Mainstreaming climate adaptation: taking stock about "what works" from empirical research worldwide</i>	Runhaar, H; Wilk, B and Wamsler, C	Regional Environmental Change	2018	48	9.6
<i>Barriers and opportunities for urban adaptation planning: analytical framework and evidence from cities in Latin America and Germany</i>	Lehmann, P; Brenck, M; and Sussbauer, E	Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change	2015	46	5.75
<i>Toward the Climate-Resilient City: Extreme Weather and Urban Climate Adaptation Policies in Two Canadian Provinces</i>	Henstra, D	Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis	2012	44	4

<i>What makes climate change adaptation effective? A systematic review of the literature</i>	Owen, G	Global Environmental Change-Human and Policy Dimensions	2020	40	13.3 3
<i>Not a panacea: private-sector engagement in adaptation and adaptation finance in developing countries</i>	Pauw, W. P.	Climate Policy	2015	39	4,88
<i>Urban partnerships and climate adaptation: challenges and opportunities</i>	Harman, BP; Taylor, BM and Lane, MB	Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	2015	39	4,88
<i>Dedicated versus mainstreaming approaches in local climate plans in Europe</i>	Reckien, D; Salvia, M and Heidrich, O	Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews	2019	36	9
<i>Toward conceptual frameworks for linking disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation</i>	Begum, RA; Sarkar, MSK; Pereira, JJ	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	2014	35	3.89
<i>Private finance for adaptation: Do private realities meet public ambitions?</i>	Pauw, W. P.; Klein, R. J. T.; Vellinga, P.& Biermann, F.	Climatic Change	2016	31	4,43
<i>Insurance models and European climate change policies: an assessment</i>	Porrini, D and Schwarze, R	European Journal of Law Economics	2014	26	2,89
<i>Varieties of market-based policy: Instrument choice in climate policy</i>	Meckling, J and Jenner, S	Environmental Politics	2016	23	3,29
<i>Mobilizing private finance for coastal adaptation: A literature review</i>	Bisaro, A and Hinkel, J	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews-Climate Change	2018	22	4,4

(Source: WoS at 23/5/22)

Supplementary File S5: Distinct key word clusters and approaches to UA financing

Table SF5: Distinct key word clusters and dominant approaches in each to UA financing (including full suite of references)

Cluster (Figure 6)	Key words & sub themes	Approaches to urban adaptation financing	Sample reference
(1)Climate finance (Renewables/Low Carbon)- Green	Banks, Business/ private investment, climate finance, capital, markets & investment, climate finance/ green finance/ green bonds, cost, economy, energy & renewable energy, instruments, Investors/pension funds, low carbon economy, market, private sector, transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low carbon & mitigation focused • Private capital markets • New instruments & mechanism (i.e., Green Bonds) & mechanisms, • Investor roles • Market regulation and fiscal policy • Private sector roles • Low carbon transition • Limited or no coverage of adaptation 	Ameli et al., 2020; Hafner et al. 2019; Mazzucato & Penna, 2016; Meckling & Jenner 2016; Monasterolo, Roventini & Foxon, 2019; Ng 2018; Pereira, 2021; Svartzman et al., 2021
(2)Insurance-Light blue	Insurance, climate transformation, loss & damages, insurance, justice, uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurance mechanisms explored • Investigation of roles for private actors and capital • International climate agreement on loss & damages. 	Bettini, Gioli & Felli, 2020; Collier et al., 2021; Collier & Cox, 2021; Han & Peng, 2021; Jarzabkowski, Chalkias & Clark, 2019; Hölscher, 2019; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Porrini & Schwarze, 2014; Regueroa et al., 2020; Soto-Montes-de-Oca, Bark & González-Arellano, 2020; Thistlethwaite, 2012; Termeer et al., 2017; Tonn et al., 2021, Zang et al., 2018; Zanotti et al. ,2020.
(2)Urban adaptation planning-Purple	Adaptive capacity, adaptation planning, adaptation strategies, city networks climate resilience, climate adaptation planning, decision-makers, integration- mitigation & adaptation planning, mitigation, Paris Agreement & UNFCC Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban adaptation focus • Planning efforts & capacity focus • Examination of resource constraints, including funding and finance • Few detailed investigations of finance types, mechanisms, and actors • Predominance of public sector funding 	Adam, Steinebach & Knill, 2018; Biesboek & Delaney, 2020; Castan, 2017; Ford & King, 2015; Heijden, 2018; Haasnott & Biesboek, 2020, Hallegatte 2008; Heijden, Picketts, 2018; Henstra, 2017; Henrstra, 2016; Leck & Robert, 2015; Lee & Painte, 2015; Lesnikowski et al., 2019; Maor, Tosun & Jordon, 2017; Maor at al., 2019; Nalau & Verrall 2021; Olazabal et al., 2019; Rashidi, Stadelmann & Patt, 2019; Revi et al. ,2014, Reckien et al., 2018 ; Root et al., 2016; Wellstead et al., 2016, Wright & Nyber 2017; Williams 2020, Zanotti et al., 2020
(4)Climate Resilience- Blue & Red	Climate resilience, capacity, community, resources for adaptation, sustainability, vulnerability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban climate resilience/adaptation focus • Planning efforts and capacity focus. • Examination of resource constraints, including funding and finance • Few detailed investigations of finance types, mechanisms, and actors • Predominance of public sector funding 	Bears & Zolnikov, 2019; Collier & Cox, 2021; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Lade, Walker & Haider, 2020; Stults & Woodruff, 2017
(5)Climate hazards-Yellow	Actors/authorities, coastal areas, flood/sea level rise, conflict, community, decision-makers, ,discourse/influence/ decision-making, hazard/risk, weather/exposure, disaster risk reduction (DRR), public sector, private sector, responsibility, value, vulnerability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate hazard focus • Flooding and sea level rise focus • Planning efforts and capacity focus • Examination of resource constraints, including funding and finance • Some investigations of finance types, mechanisms, and actors • Predominance of public sector funding • Investigation of roles for private actors and capital • Few detailed investigations of finance types and mechanisms 	Aakre et al., 2010; Adhikari, Shaila & Chalkasra, 2021; Alkhani, 2020; Basak & Werf, 2019; Bisaro et al., 2020; Birchall & Bonnett, 2020; Han & Peng, 2019; Heijden, 2018; Jordan & Huitema, 2014; Kalinowski, 2021; Klein et al., 2018; Lucas & Booth, 2020; Lee & Painter, 2015; Thistlethwaite, 2012; Tompkins & Eakin, 2012; Torabi, Dedekorkut-Howes & Howe, 2018

Note to Table S7: References are listed in S6

Supplementary File S6: Listing of core urban adaptation finance literature

List of core articles detailing financing of urban adaptation in SLR database (n=84)

(Note: Excludes all grey literature, books, and book chapters)

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Note: Excludes all grey literature, books and book chapters. Full references are listed in S5.

Supplementary File S7: Full reference list of academic articles in SLR database

Full reference list of academic articles in SLR databases

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Note: Excludes all grey literature, books and book chapters

Excluded books and book chapters

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Note: Excludes all practitioner literature

Supplementary File S8: Research gaps identified in the literature

Table S6: Adaptation finance research gaps identified in the literature (>50 research gaps in 8 themes)

Note: Grey shading denote key adaptation financing research gaps relevant to this study

Urban adaptation & climate finance literature			
Research gap		Description	Reference
Adaptation gap	Climate change adaptation gap	Further research on quantification of a climate change adaptation gap at the municipal level	Chen et al. (2016)
Climate finance governance/ policy	Climate finance policies	The academic literature on climate finance policies is limited, where it exists, focus is on North–South climate finance gap or policy analysis based on economic modelling. Advanced analysis needed of theory/practice in climate finance given importance of finance & shaping modern financial system & influence on investors/market participants.	Bhandary, Gallagher & Bowen (2011); Bowen et al. (2017) & Grubb (2011); Brahmabhatt & Steer (2016); Grubb (2011), Matsuo & Schmidt (2017), Stewart et al. (2009)
	National governance influences local adaptation policy choices	Understanding informal dimensions of national governing environments and how they influence local adaptation policy choices.	Lesnikowski et al. (2020)
	Distributional aspects of climate change impacts & policies	More research is needed on the distributional aspects of climate change impacts & policies.	Hallegatte, Henriet & Corfee-morlot (2011)
Finance sector approach	Finance sector approaches climate change issues	Knowledge lacking on how finance sector approaches climate change issues , academics with access to finance professional have shown little interest in the topic.	Christophers (2019); Diaz-Rainey et al. (2017)
Private sector & private capital	Modes of governance steering private sector & citizens adaptation activities	Modes of governance steering of private sector & citizens adaptation activities, differences between cities, comparing developing/developed country cities, examine steering between actors, relationship between the theoretical considerations & practical implications or a stronger involvement of citizens & private sector.	Klein et al. (2018)
	Risks/barriers/opportunities private investment	Risks/barriers/opportunities of private investment climate change associated with greater private investment .	Adhikari, Shaila & Chalkasra (2021)
	Private-sector involvement/governance	Patterns of private-sector involvement/governance climate adaptation/mitigation to locates gaps around delivery.	Alkhani (2020)
	Private authority displacement public authority coastal flooding	How, why & with what and the governance implications of displacement of public authorities in coastal flood protection.	Bulkeley & Schroeder (2011)
	Modes of governance steering private sector & citizens adaptation activities	Modes of governance steering of private sector & citizens adaptation activities, differences between cities, comparing developing/developed country cities, examine steering between actors, relationship between the theoretical considerations & practical implications or a stronger involvement of citizens & private sector.	Klein et al. (2018)
Finance instruments/ mechanisms	Financing mechanisms tracking planning efforts sufficiency	Track post Paris Agreement development of climate change adaptation policies & financing mechanisms - whether actual planning efforts are proving sufficient.	Olazabal et al. (2019)
	Mobilised private climate finance	What is mobilised private finance ? In advocating private adaptation finance for developed countries, can actors reach common understanding of private adaptation finance minimising norm & conflicts in a fragmented climate finance system?	Pauw (2017)
	Economic analysis of flood risk management strategies	Economic analysis of flood risk management strategies to support decisions, combine cost-benefit/robustness solutions in a meta-analysis of the economic aspects of flood risk management strategies to support decisions.	Pol, Ekko & Gabbert (2017)
	International finance climate change adaptation projects	Regional/local conditions & potential data sources in internationally financed climate change adaptation projects focusing on local communities, assessing the within-country variations of different community-focused projects.	Pomme, Biesbroek & Cebotari (2020)

	Structural incentives & governance - adaptation funding/financing mechanisms	Structural incentives/governance implications associated with the adaptation funding/financing mechanisms . Also, adaptation financing decision consequences for local accountability, equity, fiscal sustainability & effectiveness.	Keenan, Chu & Peterson (2019)
	Good characteristics of available financial tools -leverage of value, avoided costs, property values, actuarial risk & resilience metrics	In depth case studies to elucidate the opportunities/constraints for different financing approaches . Research on financing mechanisms to better capture & leverage the value of adaptation, understanding avoided costs, impacts property values, actuarial risk & resilience metrics.	Woodruff, Mullin & Roy (2020)
	Role of insurance as a climate finance mechanism	More research on the role of insurance as a climate finance mechanism.	Jarzabkowski, Konstantinos & Daniel 2019
	Collective goods interventions & tools/practices insurance	What sorts collective goods & what kinds of public interventions are officials pursuing as they conduct resilience measures drawing on the tools/practices of insurance?	Collier & Cox (2021)
	Conceptualize of self-regulation in private insurance markets	Conceptualize the emergence of self-regulation climate within private insurance markets .	Thistlethwaite (2012)
Public sector funding	Multilevel arrangements for Coastal Flood Risk Reduction (CFRR) public goods	The funding challenge necessarily involves multiple levels of government, regional nature of Coastal Flood Risk Reduction (CFRR) public goods involved, comparison of multilevel arrangements across countries, exploring the performance of public funding arrangements . Fiscal federalism multi-level governance analysis of public decision-making & fiscal authorities.	Bisaro et al. (2020)
	Public management research climate mitigation/adaptation	Call for more public management research into climate mitigation & adaptation.	Pollitt (2015); Eckersley, England & Ferry (2018)
	Flood events & disaggregated damage cost estimates	Research the implications of insufficient official information on flood events & disaggregated damage cost estimates to estimate spatially explicit flood damage. Research reasons/impacts of lack precise flood modelling in urban area.	Soto-Montes-de-Oca, Bark & González-Arellano (2020)
	Who pays for managed retreats	Who pays for managed retreats? Research on optimum approach to placing the cost burden - on the general taxpayer or on the affected communities themselves.	Noy (2020)
	Weather events & local policy change	Research on the conditions weather events generate for local policy change, insights on local policy actions resulting events.	Giordano, Boudet & Gard-Murray (2020); Crow et al. (2018); Vogel & Henstra (2015)
Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)	Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)	Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) & Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) linkages.	Begum et al. (2014)
	Interrelationships political economy factors & distribution of public funds in DRR	Understanding interrelationships between political economy factors & distribution of public funds in Disaster Relief Reduction (DRR), evaluating extent of the influence of political economy factors in DRR, measures of exogenous/endogenous variables at different periods for DRR-related fund distribution, differences of stakeholders' perceptions.	Isam et al. (2021)
	Incentivization in disaster mitigation programs	' Incentivization ' disaster mitigation programs such as insurance, mortgages & loans, tax incentives & credits, grants, regulations, & enhanced building codes - how to optimize such an incentive scheme. Also, research on integrating behavioural models of households into the design of catastrophe insurance contracts. What is the effect of developing data-driven contract pricing model, as well as sharing data between government & financial institutions, real estate agents & communities, to reduce the information bias?	Song & Wang (2020)
Adaptation planning	Integration of local climate policies/plans	Integration of local climate policies/plans in ongoing sectoral &/or development planning.	Reckien et al. (2019)
	Policy instrument arrangements in financing instrument for Climate Adaptation	Explore how planning practitioners interact with different policy instrument arrangements & the degree to which the institutional dilemmas overcome, including reducing organizational uncertainty & enforcing affirmative narratives about integrating climate adaptation measures into routines.	Root, van der Krabben & Spit (2016)
	Effective adaptation mainstreaming	Research on effective mainstreaming – there is a scarce & fragmented picture. Need to open up the black box of adaptation decision-making.	Runhaar et al. (2018); Biesbroek et al. (2015)
	Relationships of providers & beneficiaries of adaptation	Relationships between the providers & beneficiaries of adaptation , implication of individual managers of private capital taking private actions that create adaptation benefits for a broader community.	Tompkins & Eakin (2012)
	Evidence of effective adaptation (developed context)	Effective adaptation in a developed nation context & the attitudes of agents in shaping the institutions/systems & determining types of adaptation strategies. Also, what is transformational adaptation?	Torabi, Debekorkut-Howes & Howes (2019)

Weather events & local policy change	Research on the conditions weather events generate for local policy change , insights on local policy actions resulting events.	Giordono, Boudet & Gard-Murray (2020); Crow et al. (2018); Vogel & Henstra (2015)
Urban planning/development partnerships & adaptation	How urban planning/development partnerships at subregional scales incorporate adaptation objectives more explicitly/proactively. Transferability of learning's & successes given UCCA temporal nature & difficulties in observing cause-effect.	Harman, Taylor & Lane (2015)
Comparative analysis of urban climate adaptation policymaking	Comparative analysis of urban climate adaptation policymaking taking account of climate adaptation complexity & long-term nature, scientific uncertainty surrounding specific local impacts, relative indifference among citizens & conflicting ideas of appropriate scope of public action as well as challenging political dynamic .	Henstra (2012)
Policy instrument selection	Instrument selection in climate adaptation policy across different political regimes, developed/developing countries & authoritarian/democratic states, understanding effective range of policy options in different jurisdictions.	Henstra (2016)
Local politicians' perception of their role	Influence of more fundamental underlying challenges – i.e., local leadership, institutional context, & competing planning agendas –how they play out in particular local contexts, how local politicians themselves perceive role in climate adaptation.	Hjerpe & Storbjo (2015)
Effective governance processes in transformations	Climate governance & actor roles, effective governance processes, legitimacy, how effective climate governance in context of transformations supported, application of capacities framework to explore these questions.	Hölscher (2019)
Causes & consequences of climate-change impacts	Consideration of the causes & consequences of climate-change impacts more holistically.	Dabrowski (2018); Bulkeley & Tuts (2013);
Causes & consequences of climate-change impacts	Consideration of the causes & consequences of climate-change impacts more holistically.	Dabrowski (2018); Bulkeley & Tuts (2013);
Barriers to adaptation to climate change	Firstly, investigation of barriers to adaptation to climate change - origins of barriers/opportunities, employing understanding human behavior. Second, relevance of different categories of barriers & their sources. - quantitative approaches. Finally, analysis of solutions.	Lehmann et al. (2015); Biesbroek et al. (2013)
Innovative solutions (niche experiments)	Innovative solutions (niche experiments) in climate resilience solutions embedded regime on new approaches, at a faster pace & with close collaboration between key institutions.	Liu & Jensen (2017)
Challenges clashing norms in governance paradigms	Research on several challenges on the clashing norms from different governance paradigms .	Lund (2018)
Local finance challenges	Focus on establishing the precise nature of local finance challenges .	Moser et al. (2019)
Risk knowledge integration in adaptation policymaking	Understand if & how risk knowledge is being considered & integrated into current adaptation policymaking.	Sainz, De Galarraga & Olazabal (2021)
Support to local adaptation policy & planning	Investigating sub-national, regional government initiatives to support local adaptation policy/planning in Federal States, despite financial resources & constitutional responsibility to oversee municipalities.	Vogel, Henstra & McBean (2020)
Green stormwater infrastructure	Understand the inter-governmental politics & planning configurations shaping Green Stormwater Infrastructure (GSI) siting decisions.	Walker (2021)
Political aspects of policy experiments	Research the political aspects of policy experiments including pilots, the presence of multiple stakeholders & their power positions influences on the scaling up process, focus on local priorities & engagement.	Wellstead et al. (2016)
Integration of local climate policies/plans	Integration of local climate policies/plans in ongoing sectoral &/or development planning.	Reckien et al. (2019)
Effective adaptation mainstreaming	Research on effective mainstreaming – there is a scarce & fragmented picture. Need to open up the black box of adaptation decision-making.	Runhaar et al. (2018); Biesbroek et al. (2015)
Relationships of providers & beneficiaries of adaptation	Relationships between the providers & beneficiaries of adaptation , implication of individual managers of private capital taking private actions that create adaptation benefits for a broader community.	Tompkins & Eakin (2012)
Evidence of effective adaptation (developed context)	Effective adaptation in a developed nation context & the attitudes of agents in shaping the institutions/systems & determining types of adaptation strategies. Also, what is transformational adaptation ?	Torabi, Debekorkut-Howes & Howes (2019)
Weather events & local policy change	Research on the conditions weather events generate for local policy change , insights on local policy actions resulting events.	Giordono, Boudet & Gard-Murray (2020); Crow et

			al. (2018); Vogel & Henstra (2015)
	Assessment adaptation outcomes/impact	Missing component of adaptation involves the assessment of outcomes & impact.	Owen (2020)

Source: Author's empirical analysis & data

Note to Table S7: References are listed in S6

